

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON MONITORING STRUCTURAL DEFECTS IN FRPS USING GLASS FIBERS WITH CARBON NANOTUBES AND GRAPHENE COATING

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) are one of the most important materials in lightweight constructions. Glass fibers have been playing substantial roles as major reinforcements in manufacturing FRPs (GFRPs). However, the specific discrete build-ups of GFRPs make their maintenance and damage analysis a challenging task. A reliable method to evaluate the performances of GFRPs under the mechanical load is critical to optimize their maintenance schedules, assess their reliability and service life. This paper aimed to study the structural defects in composites by monitoring the deformation of reinforcements by integrating the fibers with sensory capabilities. Glass fibers coated by a thin layer of CNTs or graphene were prepared by electrophoretic deposition method, and the sensitivity of fibers to temperature and strain were studied by electrical measurement. The results showed that the coated fibers exhibited behavior with negative temperature coefficient, and the fiber with graphene coating was more sensitive to temperature than that of CNT/GF due to a higher tunneling efficiency. The fibers were exploited by embedding into epoxy for health monitoring in FRPs. The developed model composites showed significant differences on electrical response under the mechanical load, which were fundamentally associated with dimensions and conducting networks formed in the coating. The interphase controlled crack development in FRP was also discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRPs) have become one of the most important materials for engineering applications due to their high specific stiffness and strength, outstanding fatigue performance, good chemical and thermal resistance as well as low cost[1]. The interphase between the reinforcement and matrix is a key factor in controlling the properties of composites, such as functionalizing the reinforcement to get different level of bonding by making more roughness[2], different functional group [3-6], etc. For GFRPs, a common method to investigate the effect of interphase is to coat a thin film on the fibers.

In addition, nanoscale materials as fiber coating films have attracted much attention to functionalize the interphase and have been used for various purposes. As representatives, carbon nanotubes (CNT) and graphene are popular in this area due to their high aspect ratios, excellent mechanical properties, outstanding electrical and thermal conductivity, easily tailored properties [7-10]. Commonly, the electrical conductivity of glass fibers could be realized by coating these materials [6,11,12]. For other purposes, Zhang et al [11,13] showed an increase in interfacial strength of GFRP by coating CNTs to make glass fiber semiconductive, and the feasibility of employing coated fibers as strain sensor and switch were demonstrated. Liu et al[14] and Young[15] introduced strain-sensitive coatings made of CNT and epoxy to measure the stress transfer from matrix to the

fiber by studying the Raman shift of CNT under strain. Fu et al[16] used graphene as the modifier on glass fiber to offer crystallography and improve the interfacial interaction. Luo et al [12,17] showed glass fiber coated by graphite nanoplatelet or CNT to be a sensor for structural health monitor. Ma et al [18] took polymer-based nanocomposite containing CNT or graphene as coating film on glass fibers to repair surface flaws and to be barriers to environmental attacks.

Although CNT and graphene are widely researched, there are few reports on coating graphene glass fibers by EPD and few reports in doing comparison between them. As we known, the difference of structure between graphene and CNT is obvious in viewpoint of dimension, because CNT could be considered as 1-D but graphene is 2-D. Accordingly, it will be expected the different effects between them as glass fibers modifiers in the form of assembly structure.

In this paper, we deposited nanocarbon-based (CNT and Graphene) on glass fibers through electrophoretic deposition (EPD) method, then studied the effects of nanofillers on the properties of fibres and corresponding GFRPs. EPD is an effective approach in production of nanostructured films and layers on various substrates [6,19-22], such as porous materials, fiber bodies, metal and is comparatively easier comparing with other coated methods, such as spray coating[12], CVD[23]. As for different effects, we focus on the different sensitivity of electrical resistance to temperature and strain, which are closely related to the sensitive application. Related demonstrations are studied via morphology and electrical resistance change in different conditions. The fiber surface structures are detected by SEM to show the distribution and arrangement of the coating film constructed by CNT and graphene. The piezoresistivity of single coated fibers are illustrated by coupling electrical conductivity with various strain and temperature. Much attention is placed on the application of coated fibers which were embedded in epoxy to prepare model GFRPs. The mechanisms of the resulting different effects were revealed for the potential application of these functional fibers as sensor for structural health monitoring.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

E-glass fibers (GF) with an average diameter of 12 μm were used in this study. The nanotubes were multi-walled CNTs (Nanotech Port, China), and the diameter and length ranged between 20-40 nm and 5-15 μm , respectively, according to the supplier's specification. The pristine CNTs were purified in HNO_3 at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 h to remove metallic catalyst and amorphous carbon before use. Graphene was obtained by reducing graphene oxide (GO) under thermal treatment. The process for the preparation of GO can be found in Ref. [24]. Briefly, 5g graphite flakes (Asbury) were mixed with H_2SO_4 (30 mL, 98%) and fuming nitric acid (50 mL, 90%). The mixture was stirred for 24 h and separated from the solution to obtain graphite intercalation compound (GIC). The GIC was treated at 1050 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 s to obtain expanded graphite (EG). 1g EG and 200 mL H_2SO_4 were combined and stirred in a three-neck flask, followed by addition of 10 g KMnO_4 . The mixture was kept at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. Then DI water (200 mL) and later H_2O_2 (50 mL, 30%) were slowly poured into the system. The mixture was washed with DI water and following gentle ultrasonication to obtain GO suspension.

2.2 Preparation of GF with CNT and graphene coating

The coating of nanomaterials on GF was accomplished by an electrophoretic deposition (EPD) process using CNT and GO dispersion, as schematically shown in Figure 1. CNT dispersion (0.05 wt%) was prepared by sonicating CNTs into 100 mL of sodium dodecyl sulfate solution (1 mg/mL) using a Digital Sonifier (Branson Ultrasonics Corporation) for 30 min. The GO dispersion (0.05 wt%) was directly gotten by diluting the prepared GO suspension. Two copper plates (length: 12 cm, width: 6 cm, thickness: 0.3 mm) were employed as anode and cathode in EPD. Single GFs with length of 8 cm were fixed on a plastic framework mounted on the surface of anode. EPD experiment was performed under a voltage of 20V and the distance between two electrodes was kept at 10 mm. The above process was repeated on the reverse side of GF to get a homogenous coating on fiber surface. We called them as CNT/GF-B and GO/GF, which were processed at 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ in N_2 for 2h to get CNT/GF and graphene/GF.

2.3 Fabrication of model GFRP

A 80 mm coated fiber was placed in the center of a dog-bone shaped Teflon mould and connected copper wires on both fiber ends by carbon conductive paste. Epoxy monomer (Momentive, LR135) and curing agent (Momentive, LH136) were thoroughly mixed and degassed at 50 °C for 10 min prior to pouring in the mould. The sample was cured at room temperature for 24h, followed by a post curing at 65 °C for 16h. The single fiber composites are labeled as CNT-GFRP and graphene-GFRP.

2.4 Characterization

A scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Zeiss Supra55VP) was employed to characterize the morphology of GF with different coatings. The electrical properties of single fiber and model GFRP were determined using a digital multimeter (34410A, Agilent). The temperature effect on the electrical properties of single coated fiber was performed in thermostatic bath (Fluke7080) below 0k, and in an oven above 0k. The tensile test for the samples was performed on a universal testing machine (UTM, C43.104, MTS). The piezoresistance effect of fibers was evaluated by combining the electrical resistance measurement along with tensile test. For single fiber test, the specimen was placed straightly on a perforated cardboard by gluing fiber ends on conductive carbon paste, which acted as an adhesive to connect the fiber with copper wires linking with the multimeter. The specimen had a gauge length of 40 mm and a crosshead velocity of 0.5 mm/min was chosen for loading on the UTM equipped with a load cell of 10 N. For single fiber GFRP, the in-situ resistance of sample under the load was obtained by connecting copper wires at the end of composites to the multimeter along with a tensile rate of 5 mm/min on the UTM with 1 kN load cell. The gauge length of sample was 15 mm.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration showing the deposition of carbon-based nanomaterials on glass fibers using EPD method.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Morphology and electrical properties of fibers

Figure 2: SEM images of CNT or graphene coated fibers (a and b: Glass fiber coated by GO before heat treatment; c: Cross-sectional image of reduced GO coated glass fiber-Graphene/GF; d and e: Glass fiber coated by CNTs; f: CNTs-coated GF after heat treatment).

The morphology of coated fibers were characterized by SEM. Figure 2a showed that graphene had fully covered the glass fiber in layer by layer structure. For CNT-coating glass fibers, the coating was less homogeneous as compared with graphene/GF and some bare surface parts of glass fiber could be observed which indicated a not full covering from Figure 2d. These morphology differences are because graphene particles can assemble layer by layer due to plate-structure, but CNT is one dimension structure making the network full of gaps.

Thickness of coatings could be gotten from the section images of the coated fibers, and the specific value was shown in Table 1. After thermal treatment in 400 °C in N₂, the thickness of both coatings became thinner because some functional groups between particles has been removed and thermal stress occurred, making particles contacted more tightly.

Sample	CNT/GF-B	CNT/GF	GO/GF	Graphene/GF
Coating thickness (nm)	500~2000	300~600	400 ~500	200~300
Electrical Resistivity (Ω•cm)	10 ⁰ ~10 ¹	10 ⁻² ~10 ⁻¹	Infinity	10 ⁻² ~10 ⁻¹

Table 1: Thickness of coating and electrical resistivity of coated fibers.

Conductivity of coated fibers is a reflection of conductive network of CNT or graphene as measured in SEM. The electrical resistivity of glass fibers could be represented by Eq. (1) [14]

$$\rho = \frac{RS}{l} = \frac{R}{l} \cdot d \cdot 2\pi r \quad (1)$$

Where ρ is the electrical resistivity, l is the measurement length of coated fiber, R is the electrical resistance of fiber, SS is the cross section area of conductive coating, d is the thickness of coating, r

is radius of coated fiber. As shown in Table 1, ρ is in semiconductive range, much lower than single carbon nanotubes or graphene, because of the contact resistance and defects in these materials.

3.2 Effect of temperature on electrical resistance of glass fibers

Figure 3: (a) Temperature-dependent electrical resistance of CNT/GF and graphene/GF. (b) Fitting of the conductivity data based on variable range hopping (VRH) model.

To evaluate the performance under various temperature of the single coated fiber, we test the electrical resistance change in the range of 228k~423k. Figure 3a shows the effect of temperature on electrical resistance. It is obvious that both of coated fibers show a typically semiconducting behavior with a negative temperature coefficient (NTC) and the decrease rate depending on temperature can be considered to decrease substantially along with the increasing temperature. there are some theory to explain the resistance change under various temperature[24], such as ballistic conduction mechanism, conventional metallic mechanism, fluctuation-assisted tunneling and variable range hopping (VRH) [25,26]. Considering the NTC behavior of the samples in the whole temperature range and much disorder originated from defects in the CNT and Graphene as well as the contact in the conductive network, we chose VRH to explain above phenomena. The VRH model is associated with charge carriers transport by phonon-assisted tunneling between localized states in disordered materials. The disorder is produced by defects in the particles and contact between particles. The theory can be described by following equation:

$$\sigma T^{1/2} = A_0 \cdot \exp(-B/T^{-1/4}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{R} T^{1/2} = A_1 \cdot \exp(-B/T^{-1/4}) \quad (3)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{1}{R} T^{1/2}\right) \propto T^{-1/4} \quad (4)$$

Where σ is the electrical conductivity, and A_0, A_1, A_0, A_1 and B are constant, and T is absolute temperature. As shown in Figure 3b, the relationship between $\ln(\frac{1}{R} T^{1/2})$ and $T^{-1/4}$ for graphene and CNT are almost linear with linear fitting coefficients of 0.998 and 0.989, respectively, indicating that hopping mechanism is feasible to explain the conductive behavior. The NTC behaviors suggested that raising temperature made more charge carriers of higher energy level to cross the barriers between the localized states from defects in materials and contact between adjacent particles, so the tunneling rate increased which led to higher conductivity. But fitting linearity of CNT/GF was not as good as graphene/GF, showing the hopping mechanism was more appropriate for graphene samples. This difference is probably related to slight physical movement of contact points between adjacent CNTs as temperature increased.

In addition, graphene/GF is much more sensitive to temperature than CNT/GF, e.g. the change ratio of graphene/GF from 228k to 423k is 80%, much more than 20% of CNT/GF, showed in Figure 3a. We get the parameter from Figure 3b show that graphene/GF have higher B (Graphene/GF is 58.0, CNT/GF is 18.8), which is associated with higher tunneling efficiency. From structural perspective, the difference is possibly because the overlapped area between graphene layers is much larger due to their 2-D structure than point-to-point among CNT, so the electrons have higher possibility to cross the thinner barrier in Graphene coating. Considering the sensitivity and the size (diameter~12 μ m) of the samples, the samples can be used as temperature sensor in microscale.

3.3 Piezoresistance effect of coated glass fibers

Figure 4: (a) Strain-stress curve of single coated fibers. (b) Relationship between electrical resistance and strain of coated fibers

Figure 4 shows the coupled electrical-mechanical tensile test results for single fiber. From the figure, the piezoresistive property of the fibers is demonstrated by the resistance rising linearly with strain increasing. The sensitivity is defined as gauge factor by:

$$K = \frac{R(\varepsilon) - R_0}{R_0} / \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

Where ε is the applied strain, R_0 is resistance of fiber before deformation and $R(\varepsilon)$ is the resistance at the strain ε . Gauge factor is 2.27 ± 0.10 , 9.53 ± 0.40 in the whole strain range for CNT/GF and Graphene /GF, respectively. The key factors dominating the positive piezoresistivity of fibers include: i) the intrinsic electrical conductivity change induced by deformation of CNT or graphene; ii) the number variation of conductive paths; iii) the contact resistance variation caused by the separation between neighboring CNT or graphene particles. It is negligible to consider i) or intrinsic electrical conductivity change of CNT and Graphene. According to the studies, gauge factor of CNT or Graphene is much different from our data, as Graphene is about 2~3 [27,28], CNT is over 100 [29]. ii) and iii) are the dominating factors for these behaviors [30-35] caused by strain.

In addition, graphene/GF is more sensitive than CNT/GF. The similar phenomena are also reported by Luo [36], but there is no specific reason for that. Here we get some implications from the work [37]. The possible reason is due to the different structure of the coatings. As demonstrated by SEM, the coating in CNT/GF is porous and loose, causing slippage between CNT particles and reforming conductive paths when CNT/GF is in stretched state. It is envisaged that when applying strain to samples, some effective slide between carbon nanotubes could make the resistance larger; but there are slides which could make resistance less increased even decreased by keeping contact with changing mutual contact position or obtaining more contacts in slide process of adjacent particles. Another way is that stretching makes some tangled nanotubes change from un-contact to contact state to lower the

resistance by forming new conductive paths or makes some contacted tubes more tight, which also caused resistance decrease. For graphene/GF, the coating is more compacted in layer by layer form, not like the loose and porous state of CNT/GF. In such circumstances, stretching only enlarges distance between graphene, leading to an increase in resistance without other effect as that in network of CNT/GF, which created larger gauge factor of graphene/GF as comparing with CNT/GF.

3.4 Application of coated fibers for the health monitoring of GFRP

Figure 5: (a) Picture of single fiber composite sample. (b) Piezoresistive response of coated glass fibers. (c) Cyclic piezoresistive test of CNT-GFRP. (d) Cyclic piezoresistive test of graphene-GFRP.

Figure 6: Schematic of interphase structures of CNT-GFRP and graphene-GFRP

To compare the performance of CNT/GF and Graphene/GF as strain sensor and monitoring the damage of composites, we made single fiber composites by embedding single coated fiber in epoxy as shown in Figure 5a. While applying the tensile strain, the piezoresistivity of the samples were

evaluated. Here we can regard the carbon coating on glass fiber as “interphase” between the fiber and polymer matrix.

Figure 5b showed the resistance and stress change of single fiber composites at different strain. For simplicity, we just used one stress-strain curve of the samples as the representative of CNT-GFRP and graphene-GFRP. We divided the piezoresistive behavior into several stages (CNT-GFRP consists of two stages, graphene-GFRP consists of three stages):

i) At small strain (below 1.3% for CNT, 1.5% for Graphene samples), the resistance of both samples increased with increasing strain, but gauge factor is 8.3 ± 3.0 , 5.0 ± 1.0 for CNT and graphene, respectively. Gauge factors of single fiber composites are different from standalone fibers in Section 3.3: CNT-GFRP is largely more than CNT/GF while graphene-GFRP is less than Graphene/GF. For graphene-GFRP, it is because of Poisson effect [17]. When the sample is under the tensile strain, the vertical direction to surface of glass fiber is under compression making layer distance in this orientation decreased which limited electrical resistance going up; so the combination of the tension and compression effect decreased sensitivity as comparing standalone fibers. For CNT-GFRP, it is because that the coating structure is different from that of CNT/GF, which was discussed later.

ii) At larger strain, electrical resistance of CNT samples ($>1.3\%$) quickly turned to “infinity” (The resistance is out of measurable range), indicating CNT networks broke up in very short time (less than 1s in the experiment); but for the graphene samples ($>1.5\%$), strain sensitivity starkly became larger (Gauge factor ~ 130). For the different phenomena between the two samples in stage ii), we considered the interphase structures between CNT and Graphene samples, shown in Figure 6. Interphase of graphene-GFRP could be considered to only consist of graphene layers. That is because graphene covered glass fiber tightly and almost completely layer by layer, so epoxy hardly penetrates into the Graphene coating. In this case, When applied strain is small ($< 1.5\%$), the interphase deformed due to load transfer from epoxy and interlayer to make electrical resistance go up. When the strain is larger, interphase suffered larger deformation due to stress concentration caused by breakup of glass fiber/local plastic deformation of epoxy. Considering interphase structure in layer by layer, graphene particles can slide against each other among layers to withstand very large strain; accordingly, the electrical resistance increased gradually without sudden turning into infinity. For interphase of CNT sample, CNT coating is full of gap and porous, so epoxy can penetrate into the gaps to form the interphase in new structure-mixture of CNT and epoxy, as shown in Figure 6. When applied strain, the conductive interphase deformed. It is reasonable that the conductive network ruptures in sudden form and in a very small strain range when the tensile strain is larger than a critical value, making the resistance from measurable to non-measurable in very short period, showing crack paths are considered as in the vertical direction to glass fiber as illustrated in Figure 6. In addition, the structure also can explain the large gauge factor of CNT-GFRP than CNT/GF as mentioned before. In the case, CNT particles are fixed by epoxy in the conductive network, when CNT-GFRP is under strain, so the factors making resistance decrease as stated in section 3.3 were eliminated. In the case, distance change between CNT particles is deformation of epoxy between CNT particles, which caused higher gauge factor.

iii) Graphene samples show non conductivity at the same time as the fracture of the epoxy, showing strain elongation of Graphene interphase exceeds elongation of epoxy. To further compare the different performance in detecting damage in fiber/epoxy, we measured the resistance change of the single coated fiber composites under cyclic strain applied with increasing strain peaks. As shown in Figure 5c the variation of resistance and strain could return to the original value after unloading when CNT-GFRP is in the first and second cycles with strain less than 1%, showing the reversible deformation of interphase. When applied strain became larger, resistance change showed irreversible behavior as same as applied strain for both of samples, suggesting the occurrence of permanent deformation/damage in conductive network. With further rising of loading peak, the more residual $\Delta R/R_0$, the more damage accumulation. And when strain reached critical strain point, CNT-GFRP suddenly turned to non-conductive and then turned to conductive again below the critical point-the “switch effect” in a cycle period as reported in Ref.[]. Specially, behavior of CNT-GFRP in the fifth cycle is different from “switch effect” of the fourth cycle - here we call it “hysteresis effect”- because the sample could not turn to conductive before end of this cycle from nonconductive. It takes about another 40min after unloading to be conductive again. The mechanism for “hysteresis effect” is

because of hysteresis in microscale of polymer chains, indicating that mechanical behavior of CNT network was controlled by epoxy movement, which is consistent with interphase structure of CNT-GFRP illustrated in Figure 6. For the phenomena, it can be used as a timer or rendering some help to study the motion of the chain of polymer.

Shown in Figure 5d, with strain peak increase, graphene-GFRP also showed the reversible behavior at small strain (cycle 1, 2) and irreversible behavior (cycle 3, 4) at large strain and could go up drastically (cycle 5 and 6) at the critical strain point. Different slope of resistance change responded to the states of composites located, and the large gauge factor means the damage occurred inside the model composites. The irreversible resistance change became larger with increasing strain peak, indicating more damage accumulation in graphene networks at large strain. In addition, graphene-GFRP displayed less delayed action compared to CNT-GFRP, demonstrating conductive network is dominated by graphene layers. Considering the large elongation of conductive network of graphene-GFRP, we speculated that crack developed paths are almost parallel to glass fiber, as shown in Figure 6. From this view, this kind interphase made of layer structure could be regarded as the weak interphase possessing the large deformation.

In summary, obvious different behaviors of the CNT-GFRP and graphene-GFRP are caused by the different coating structure which is due to the dimensional differences of CNT and graphene. By employing these differences, it is possible to monitor failure modes in composites and design composites with different crack paths. For detecting damage in composites, graphene-GFRP could obtain more details about the damage process and be more optimistic in practical applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We deposited CNT or graphene coatings on surface of glass fiber by EPD method to make fibers sensitive to temperature and strain. CNT or graphene networks formed on fiber surface make them conductive. In the networks, CNTs touched each other by point to point or line to line connection, while graphene formed layer-by-layer structure which tightly covered on glass fiber. Graphene exhibited higher sensitivity to temperature and strain than that of CNT samples, which can be explained from the different coating structure of networks. The application of CNT or graphene coated glass fiber as strain sensor was performed by embedding single coated fibers into epoxy. The piezoresistivity of single fiber composites are different from that of corresponding standalone coated fibers and also different between CNT-GFRP and graphene-GFRP, which could be explained by different interphase structure. Interphase of CNT-GFRP is mixture of CNT particles and epoxy while that of graphene-GFRP is only graphene layers. The damage mechanism of interphase was proposed, graphene/GF and graphene-GFRP were more practical as strain sensor for the early warning of damages in FRP structures.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Sureeyatanapas, M. Hejda, S.J. Eichhorn and R.J. Young, Comparing single-walled carbon nanotubes and samarium oxide as strain sensors for model glass-fibre/epoxy composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **70**, 2010, pp. 88-93 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2009.09.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2009.09.009)).
- [2] R. Wang, Z. Li, W. Liu, W. Jiao, L. Hao and F. Yang, Attapulgite-graphene oxide hybrids as thermal and mechanical reinforcements for epoxy composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **87**, 2013, pp. 29-35 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.08.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.08.002)).
- [3] P.C. Ma, Q.B. Zheng, E. Mader and J.K. Kim, Behavior of load transfer in functionalized

- carbon nanotube/epoxy nanocomposites, *Polymer*, **53**, 2012, pp. 6081-6088 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymer.2012.10.053](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2012.10.053)).
- [4] P.C. Ma, S.Y. Mo, B.Z. Tang and J.K. Kim, Dispersion, interfacial interaction and re-agglomeration of functionalized carbon nanotubes in epoxy composites, *Carbon*, **48**, 2010, pp. 1824-1834 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2010.01.028](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2010.01.028)).
- [5] P.C. Ma, J.K. Kim and B.Z. Tang, Effects of silane functionalization on the properties of carbon nanotube/epoxy nanocomposites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67**, 2007, pp. 2965-2972 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2007.05.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2007.05.006)).
- [6] Q. An, A.N. Rider and E.T. Thostenson, Hierarchical Composite Structures Prepared by Electrophoretic Deposition of Carbon Nanotubes onto Glass Fibers, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **5**, 2013, pp. 2022-2032 (doi: [10.1021/am3028734](https://doi.org/10.1021/am3028734)).
- [7] Y. Zhu, S. Murali, W. Cai, X. Li, J.W. Suk, J.R. Potts and R.S. Ruoff, Graphene and Graphene Oxide: Synthesis, Properties, and Applications, *Advanced Materials*, **22**, 2010, pp. 3906-3924 (doi: [10.1002/adma.201001068](https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201001068)).
- [8] P.-C. Ma and Y. Zhang, Perspectives of carbon nanotubes/polymer nanocomposites for wind blade materials, *Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews*, **30**, 2014, pp. 651-660 (doi: [10.1016/j.rser.2013.11.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.11.008)).
- [9] P.-C. Ma, N.A. Siddiqui, G. Marom and J.-K. Kim, Dispersion and functionalization of carbon nanotubes for polymer-based nanocomposites: A review, *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **41**, 2010, pp. 1345-1367 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.07.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.07.003)).
- [10] Z. Han and A. Fina, Thermal conductivity of carbon nanotubes and their polymer nanocomposites: A review, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **36**, 2011, pp. 914-944 (doi: [10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2010.11.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2010.11.004)).
- [11] J. Zhang, R. Zhuang, J. Liu, E. Maeder, G. Heinrich and S. Gao, Functional interphases with multi-walled carbon nanotubes in glass fibre/epoxy composites, *Carbon*, **48**, 2010, pp. 2273-2281 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2010.03.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2010.03.001)).
- [12] S.D. Luo, W. Obitayo and T. Liu, SWCNT-thin-film-enabled fiber sensors for lifelong structural health monitoring of polymeric composites - From manufacturing to utilization to failure, *Carbon*, **76**, 2014, pp. 321-329 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2014.04.083](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2014.04.083)).
- [13] J. Zhang, J.W. Liu, R.C. Zhuang, E. Mader, G. Heinrich and S.L. Gao, Single MWNT-Glass Fiber as Strain Sensor and Switch, *Advanced Materials*, **23**, 2011, pp. 3392-+ (doi: [10.1002/adma.201101104](https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201101104)).
- [14] L. Liu, P.C. Ma, M. Xu, S.U. Khan and J.K. Kim, Strain-sensitive Raman spectroscopy and electrical resistance of carbon nanotube-coated glass fibre sensors, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 1548-1555 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.06.002)).
- [15] P. Sureeyatanapas and R.J. Young, SWNT composite coatings as a strain sensor on glass fibres in model epoxy composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 1547-1552 (doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.08.002](https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.08.002)).
- [16] N. Ning, W. Zhang, J. Yan, F. Xu, T. Wang, H. Su, C. Tang and Q. Fu, Largely enhanced crystallization of semi-crystalline polymer on the surface of glass fiber by using graphene oxide as a modifier, *Polymer*, **54**, 2013, pp. 303-309 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymer.2012.11.045](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2012.11.045)).
- [17] S. Luo and T. Liu, Graphite Nanoplatelet Enabled Embeddable Fiber Sensor for in Situ Curing Monitoring and Structural Health Monitoring of Polymeric Composites, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **6**, 2014, pp. 9314-9320 (doi: [10.1021/am5017039](https://doi.org/10.1021/am5017039)).
- [18] P.-C. Ma, J.-W. Liu, S.-L. Gao and E. Maeder, Development of functional glass fibres with nanocomposite coating: A comparative study, *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **44**, 2013, pp. 16-22 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2012.08.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2012.08.027)).
- [19] S.-Y. Huang, G.-P. Wu, C.-M. Chen, Y. Yang, S.-C. Zhang and C.-X. Lu, Electrophoretic deposition and thermal annealing of a graphene oxide thin film on carbon fiber surfaces, *Carbon*, **52**, 2013, pp. 613-616 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2012.09.062](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2012.09.062)).
- [20] J.K. Park, I.-H. Do, P. Askeland and L.T. Drzal, Electrodeposition of exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets onto carbon fibers and properties of their epoxy composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 1734-1741 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.02.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.02.002)).
- [21] A.R. Boccaccini, J. Cho, J.A. Roether, B.J.C. Thomas, E.J. Minay and M.S.P. Shaffer,

- Electrophoretic deposition of carbon nanotubes, *Carbon*, **44**, 2006, pp. 3149-3160 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2006.06.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2006.06.021)).
- [22] M. Wang, L.D. Duong, J.-S. Oh, N.T. Mai, S. Kim, S. Hong, T. Hwang, Y. Lee and J.-D. Nam, Large-area, Conductive and Flexible Reduced Graphene Oxide (RGO) Membrane Fabricated by Electrophoretic Deposition (EPD), *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2014, pp. (doi: [10.1021/am404719u](https://doi.org/10.1021/am404719u)).
- [23] Q. Song, K.Z. Li, H.L. Li, H.J. Li and C. Ren, Grafting straight carbon nanotubes radially onto carbon fibers and their effect on the mechanical properties of carbon/carbon composites, *Carbon*, **50**, 2012, pp. 3949-3952 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2012.03.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2012.03.023)).
- [24] A.B. Kaiser and V. Skakalova, Electronic conduction in polymers, carbon nanotubes and graphene, *Chemical Society Reviews*, **40**, 2011, pp. 3786-3801 (doi: [10.1039/c0cs00103a](https://doi.org/10.1039/c0cs00103a)).
- [25] Q. Li, Y. Li, X. Zhang, S.B. Chikkannanavar, Y. Zhao, A.M. Dangelewicz, L. Zheng, S.K. Doorn, Q. Jia, D.E. Peterson, P.N. Arendt and Y. Zhu, Structure-dependent electrical properties of carbon nanotube fibers, *Advanced Materials*, **19**, 2007, pp. 3358+ (doi: [10.1002/adma.200602966](https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.200602966)).
- [26] S. Luo, T. Liu, S.M. Benjamin and J.S. Brooks, Variable range hopping in single-wall carbon nanotube thin films: a processing-structure-property relationship study, *Langmuir*, **29**, 2013, pp. 8694-8702 (doi: [10.1021/la401264r](https://doi.org/10.1021/la401264r)).
- [27] M.Y. Huang, T.A. Pascal, H. Kim, W.A. Goddard and J.R. Greer, Electronic-Mechanical Coupling in Graphene from in situ Nanoindentation Experiments and Multiscale Atomistic Simulations, *Nano Letters*, **11**, 2011, pp. 1241-1246 (doi: [10.1021/nl104227t](https://doi.org/10.1021/nl104227t)).
- [28] A.D. Smith, F. Niklaus, A. Paussa, S. Vaziri, A.C. Fischer, M. Sterner, F. Forsberg, A. Delin, D. Esseni, P. Palestri, M. Ostling and M.C. Lemme, Electromechanical Piezoresistive Sensing in Suspended Graphene Membranes, *Nano Letters*, **13**, 2013, pp. 3237-3242 (doi: [10.1021/nl401352k](https://doi.org/10.1021/nl401352k)).
- [29] J. Cao, Q. Wang and H.J. Dai, Electromechanical properties of metallic, quasimetallic, and semiconducting carbon nanotubes under stretching, *Physical Review Letters*, **90**, 2003, pp. 1-7 (doi: [10.1103/PhysRevLett.90.157601](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.90.157601)).
- [30] L.M. Chiacchiarelli, M. Rallini, M. Monti, D. Puglia, J.M. Kenny and L. Torre, The role of irreversible and reversible phenomena in the piezoresistive behavior of graphene epoxy nanocomposites applied to structural health monitoring, *Composites Science and Technology*, **80**, 2013, pp. 73-79 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.03.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.03.009)).
- [31] M. Park, H. Kim and J.P. Youngblood, Strain-dependent electrical resistance of multi-walled carbon nanotube/polymer composite films, *Nanotechnology*, **19**, 2008, pp. 157601-157604 (doi: [10.1088/0957-4484/19/05/055705](https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/19/05/055705)).
- [32] T. Yasuoka, Y. Shimamura and A. Todoroki, Electrical Resistance Change under Strain of CNF/Flexible-Epoxy Composite, *Advanced Composite Materials*, **19**, 2010, pp. 123-138 (doi: [10.1163/092430410x490446](https://doi.org/10.1163/092430410x490446)).
- [33] N. Hu, Y. Karube, C. Yan, Z. Masuda and H. Fukunaga, Tunneling effect in a polymer/carbon nanotube nanocomposite strain sensor, *Acta Mater.*, **56**, 2008, pp. 2929-2936 (doi: [10.1016/j.actamat.2008.02.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2008.02.030)).
- [34] X. Li, R. Zhang, W. Yu, K. Wang, J. Wei, D. Wu, A. Cao, Z. Li, Y. Cheng, Q. Zheng, R.S. Ruoff and H. Zhu, Stretchable and highly sensitive graphene-on-polymer strain sensors, *Scientific Reports*, **2**, 2012, pp. (doi: [10.1038/srep00870](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep00870)).
- [35] T.C. Theodosiou and D.A. Saravanos, Numerical investigation of mechanisms affecting the piezoresistive properties of CNT-doped polymers using multi-scale models, *Composites Science and Technology*, **70**, 2010, pp. 1312-1320 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2010.04.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2010.04.003)).
- [36] S. Luo and T. Liu, SWCNT/Graphite Nanoplatelet Hybrid Thin Films for Self-Temperature-Compensated, Highly Sensitive, and Extensible Piezoresistive Sensors, *Advanced Materials*, **25**, 2013, pp. 5650-5657 (doi: [10.1002/adma.201301796](https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201301796)).
- [37] M.Z. Seyedin, J.M. Razal, P.C. Innis and G.G. Wallace, Strain-Responsive Polyurethane/PEDOT:PSS Elastomeric Composite Fibers with High Electrical Conductivity, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **24**, 2014, pp. 2957-2966 (doi: [10.1002/adfm.201303905](https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201303905)).